

Power, Control, and State (De)Formation under Hayat Tahrir al-Sham

Salam Said

Salam Said is a Syrian academic and economist with expertise in Arab economies and the political economy of Syria, particularly post-war reconstruction. Said has published various academic and policy papers focusing on political economy and geopolitical analysis in Syria.

Syria is currently undergoing a historic transition: a crucial state (re)formation after fourteen years of war that destroyed a large part of the Syrian economy and displaced over half of the population. Moreover, the takeover of Damascus by Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) does not represent a transition from a repressive military dictatorship to a democratic state grounded in citizenship and the rule of law. Rather, it reflects the reproduction of coercive and unjust power structures that have dominated Syria for the past fifty years, with only a redistribution of roles among those in power and between victims and perpetrators, without substantive transformation of the underlying political order.

This paper analyzes the current transitional leadership under Ahmed al-Sharaa, rebel leader of HTS, based on Michael Mann's concepts of "infrastructural" and "despotic" state sources of power. Infrastructural power, grounded in institutional cooperation with society and efficient provision of services, contrasts with despotic power, which relies on coercion and violence by the ruling elite to control society. While both forms often coexist, an overreliance on despotic power increases the risk of state failure, whereas strengthening infrastructural power enhances state resilience (Mann 1984).

The Syrian state under HTS's transitional leadership is relying heavily on violence to assert control over its territories. At this critical juncture of state reshaping—requiring exceptional capacity to navigate internal and geopolitical challenges—the state has failed to build institutions, gain public trust, or operate as more than a militia.

Consolidation of Power

By reclaiming power through "revolutionary legitimacy" in February 2025 (Ziade 2025) and later through "transitional legitimacy," based on a controversial constitutional declaration that granted the president virtually unlimited authorities (HRW 2025), transitional president al-Sharaa has centralized and concentrated power in unprecedented ways—holding multiple key posts simultaneously, including President, quasi-Prime Minister, head of the armed forces, chair of the Supreme Judicial Council, head of the Sovereign Wealth Fund, and chair of the National Development Fund. In addition to holding both executive and judicial authorities, he is poised to dominate parliamentary decision-making by directly appointing 30% of its members. At all state levels, appointments are made by al-Sharaa's inner circle, echoing the exclusionary practices of the Asad era. Genuine participa-

tion and bottom-up governance are absent (Haid 2025).

Fragile state institutions have been further weakened and infiltrated by HTS members since December 2024. Experts working closely with the transitional government report highly centralized decision-making, marked by a lack of transparency and accountability. Ministers unaffiliated with HTS hold little genuine authority, as members in less visible roles—reporting directly to al-Sharaa’s inner circle—dictate key decisions. They report the creation of “parallel bodies” led by HTS that routinely override state institutions (personal conversation 2025a).

HTS consolidates power over the economy through clientelism and the placement of relatives in key positions.¹ This reproduces political-economic patterns of inequality and cronyism seen under Asad, as the business network around al-Sharaa relocated from Idlib to Damascus, and began to receive privileges in looting public resources and dominating the market. Sham Bank, for instance, a private bank established by HTS in 2018 in Idlib, holds now a privileged market share position and is contracted to handle public salaries. It appears to operate as a parallel “Central Bank.”²

The neoliberal policies adopted by HTS have reinforced this “state capture” through privatization, outsourcing of basic services, and opaque investment agreements with interna-

tional firms. A free market for HTS does not necessarily mean competition; rather, it often means that business companies owned by the elite enjoy monopolies and operate outside the rule of law (Al-Khatib 2024). To date, there is no information on how state assets—particularly properties of the Ministry of Defense and the Ministry of Awqaf—are managed.

HTS fighters, who are meanwhile employees of the interior and defense ministries, receive salaries three to four times higher than those of ordinary civil servants, along with housing and other benefits.³ These benefits can secure loyalty to the leadership and are likely to result in the accumulation of wealth within HTS circles. Recruitment into the privileged armed forces is highly selective and follows strict ideological criteria. According to an applicant, “You have to be one of them,” meaning aligned with HTS ideology (Personal conversation 2025b).

Beyond economic control, HTS increasingly relies on ideology to consolidate dominance by promoting its interpretation of Islam and national identity. Military training embeds ideological instruction that excludes Syrians with differing beliefs, while religious institutions such as the Ministry of Awqaf and the High Islamic Council have seen personnel replaced to align with this agenda. Although the government officially advocates a moderate religious discourse, HTS propaganda reinforces its own narrative by tolerating hate

1 The president’s brothers hold key positions, including Chairman of the Investment Authority and Secretary-General to the Presidency, while his brother-in-law serves as Secretary of the new Syrian Central Bank (Enab Baladi 2025a).

2 See e.g. Al Modon (2025).

3 There is no official publication regarding the salaries of HTS fighters. However, in personal conversations with two applicants for the armed Forces in February in Damascus, they mentioned that the salary would be \$125. They also stated that HTS fighters earn between \$200 and \$400 per month, depending on rank. Employees in the public sector earn between \$20 and \$120. The latter is a salary for professor at the university. (Eqtsad. 2025 and The Arab Weekly 2025)

speech and sectarian mobilization against moderate Islam and other faiths—most evident during the coastal massacres in March and in as-Sweida in July (Enab Baladi 2025b, STJ 2025).

The de facto power consolidation contradicts the promises conveyed by al-Sharaa in his speeches regarding participation, inclusivity, and justice. In particular, women—who were encouraged by the president’s “inclusive and gender-sensitive” first speech—are deeply disappointed by the limited women’s representation in key positions and the shrinking public spaces for women (Hassan 2025, Asad 2025). This frustration is shared by political parties, journalists, and activists, who face persistent challenges in the absence of clear regulation of their work, reviving memories of the climate of fear that prevailed under the previous regime (Hamou 2025).

Despotic Power

The transitional leadership under al-Sharaa has shown a profound inability to formulate or implement state policies, undermining the infrastructural power of the state. For instance, committees on transitional justice and reconstruction exist but have produced no tangible outcomes. No public prosecutions for crimes against humanity have been pursued, and no national plan addresses socioeconomic challenges such as poverty, unemployment, or refugee repatriation. Service provision as a key mechanism for strengthening state-society trust is entirely absent, and the promised new social contract has not been negotiated. International pledges of hundreds of millions of dollars in investment remain unfulfilled, recalling Asad’s reconstruction rhetoric since 2018. Given Syria’s persistent political instability and incapacity to repair fundamental infrastructure, such

investment contracts are unlikely to materialize.

These patterns also recall HTS’s governance in Idlib during the war, where the group pursued a neoliberal model in which service provision was framed as charity rather than as a right. This approach left war-torn communities to cope with essential needs such as healthcare, water, and electricity largely through INGO support, while state resources are diverted toward administration and military operations (Al-Zaraee and Shaar 2021). Now, with the reduction and elimination of humanitarian aid from global North countries, INGO support may not even be forthcoming.

The leadership in Damascus relies heavily on a despotic conception of the state, deriving power primarily from coercion and centralization. To assert control over Syrian territories, HTS employs a militarized approach, disregarding diplomacy or genuine dialogue. Military operations on the coast, in the Damascus suburbs, and in as-Sweida reveal that official forces often function as militias driven by ideological zeal rather than disciplined armies. According to the UN Commission of Inquiry on Syria, these forces have committed crimes and human rights violations systematically (*OHCHR 2025*), including the brutal killing of civilians and looting of property, reflecting ideological motives. The human toll of these operations together exceeded 3,500 killed and hundreds of thousands displaced since March 2025 (see reports of SOHR 2025). This approach was adopted by the previous regime in 2011 and proved ineffective in maintaining power or achieving stability.

HTS employs sectarianism and social polarization to consolidate power and neutralize

rivals through loyalty-building. Sectarianism, institutionalized in Syria during the Ottoman and French colonial periods to weaken national resistance, was also extensively used by the Asad regime (Kastrinou 2016). This approach empowers religious, ethnic, and tribal leaders to represent their communities more than political leaders who embody common political values across religions and ethnicities.

Geopolitical actors, including Israel and Turkey, have exploited these divisions to strengthen their negotiating leverage within Syria. Such interventions threaten not only national integrity, which HTS claims to uphold, but also social cohesion and a shared Syrian identity. Calls for decentralization in northeastern Syria and in as-Sweida reflect the consequences of these policies (Kastrinou and Said 2025). Consequently, the central leadership in Damascus risks losing its legitimacy as a representative of all Syrians, further exposing state dysfunction and undermining public acceptance of coercive authority.

Conclusion

HTS has relied on coercion, sectarian and gender exclusion, and systemic violence instead of dialogue, trust, and institution-building. By prioritizing despotic power over infrastructural power—focusing on security and coercion while failing to provide essential services or build functional institutions—this transitional leadership undermines social cohesion and threatens Syria's stability. The deliberate hollowing out and predation of state institutions and targeting of populations with differing values or beliefs demonstrates a systematic, rather than individual, approach to control, exemplifying the deformation of the state. ♦

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